

Oxidation degradation of GFRP

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SUMMARY

In this study, the promotional experiment on degradation using an oven was executed to investigate a degradation behavior of GFRP under high temperature and bending tests of the GFRP with heating attack were examined. As a result, it was found that color change didn't show the decrease of strength change.

Keywords: oxidation, degradation, weight change, color change, bending strength

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, FRPs (Fiber Reinforced Plastics) are used for various structural part in terms of superior mechanical strength, corrosion resistance, water proof and light stability, and the number of the application keeps increasing every years ^[1,2]. Considering that FRP is used for structural part, the use of long-term must be ensured because there is a possibility of causing a serious accident due to short life such as degradation and fatigue fracture. Especially, because the application to the transportation is active recently, the keyword of "durability" is an important factor, and many researches have been carried out for the durability of composite materials.

In FRP material, GFRPs (glass fiber reinforced plastics) have been applied for tanks and stacks for a long time. Especially, the products past 20 or 30 years still exist in the stacks. However, as mentioned above, because the durability of FRP is not clarified in detail, the design of GFRP is overestimated or underestimated in the present condition. Moreover, because the criteria of exchange still depend on the user's subjective judgement such as change of color, state of appearance and time of use, many serious accidents might be caused in the future. Therefore, the clarification of detailed service life of GFRP is necessity. Now, the service life of GFRP used in tanks and stacks is assumed to 30 years. However, the product which can be used for long-term such as 50 years is also required in the market. That is to say, it is most necessary to reveal the mechanism of the various degradations in the GFRP to satisfy their request and it is necessary to accumulate the degradation data.

In this study, the oxidation degradation was noticed as one of the fundamental researches to establish the durability of GFRP, and the degradation behaviour of GFRP was investigated by promoting the degradation such as severe condition of high temperature. The behaviour was discussed from the result of appearance, the change of color and weight, three-point bending properties. Moreover, the degradation mechanism was revealed based on precise cross-sectional observation of the degradation area by optical microscope and SEM and FT-IR analysis of cured specimen.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Three kinds of resin, two unsaturated polyester resins; R200 and 150HRBQTN (JAPAN COMPOSITE CO., LTD) and vinylester resin; R806 (SHOWA HIGHPOLYMER CO., LTD) were chosen as the matrix. Each resin characteristic is shown in Table 1. In specimens, GFRP with 3mm thickness were used. Figure 1 shows a schematic illustration of the specimen. In the GFRP, surface mat of 1ply and chopped strand mat of 3ply were laminated and were made by hand lay-up method. And specimens were cut into 15mm width and 90mm length.

In experimental method, specimens were cured at the temperature 100, 150, 200 and 250 degrees for 500h and 1000h respectively. To investigate the degradation behaviour, color differences and weight change was evaluated by using Konica Minolta Holdings, Inc., CR200 and A&D, HR202i respectively. And three-point bending properties of the cured specimens was evaluated by using INSTRON 55R4206 to compare with that of no-cure specimen. The span length of bending test was 60mm. Also, Acoustic Emission (AE) under the bending test was measured by using AE measuring equipment (NF Corporation, AE tester 9501) to measure how the level of the micro damage changed as shown in Figure 2. Finally, the degradation mechanism was discussed by the observation of cross-section and SEM in cured specimen.

Table 1 Characteristics of each resin

Kinds of Resin		Thermal resistance	Corrosion resistance
R200	Isophthalic Type Unsaturated Polyester (JAPAN COMPOSITE Co., LTD.)	×	×
150HRBQTN	Isophthalic Type Unsaturated Polyester (SHOWA HIGH POLYMER)	○	×
R806	Vinylester (SHOWA HIGH POLYMER)	△	○

○ : Good △ : Normal × : Bad

Figure 1 Schematic illustration of GFRP specimen

Figure 2 AE sensor location under three-point bending test

RESULTS

State of Appearance

Figure 3 (a) and (b) show the photographs after cure for 1000h in each temperature on R806 specimen as typical degradation behaviour. As for the upper view, in the exposure time of both 500h and 1000h, as the exposure temperature was high, the color of an appearance of all specimens changed from the primary color to brown color. And their specimens were carbonized and the color of the appearance was black color above exposure temperature 200 degrees. As for the side view, in the exposure time of both 500h and 1000h, it was observed that all specimens was degraded from external area of the specimen. Especially, in the specimen with R806 resin, the phenomenon that the surface was carbonized but internal area was not carbonized was observed remarkably. As these results, it was found that the degree of the degradation was different by a kind of resin.

Figure 3 Photographs of R806 specimen after cure for 1000h in each temperature

Numerical Analysis in Change of Color

Numerical analysis in the change of color to investigate the difference in detail was carried out by using testing machine. The definition of the numerical value for the change of color in the testing machine was calculated by below formula (1).

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{((L - L_0)^2 + (a - a_0)^2 + (b - b_0)^2)} \quad (1)$$

Here, ΔE is the quantity of the change of color,

L is the degree of brightness in the objective

L_0 is the degree of criterial brightness

a is the degree of the color in the range from red to green in the objective

a_0 is the degree of the criterial color in the range from red to green

b is the degree of the color in the range from blue to yellow in the objective

b_0 is the degree of the criterial color in the range from blue to yellow

Figure 5 (a), (b) and (c) show the relationship between the quantity of the change of color and each exposure temperature in each specimen. In all specimens, the quantity of the change increased drastically until exposure temperature 150°C and decreased suddenly in the higher temperature than 150°C in the case of both 500h and 1000h. Especially, in the specimen with 150HRBQTN, the drastic change of color was seen in the range between 100°C and 150°C.

Figure 5 Relationship between the quantity of the change of color and each exposure temperature in each specimen

Investigation of Change of Weight

Next, the change of weight for each exposure temperature in each specimen was investigated. Relationships between the ratio of weight change and the exposure temperature in exposure time 500h and 1000h are shown in Figure 6 (a), (b) and (c). Here, the mass of approximate glass fiber was not involved to check the change of the only resin weight. In all specimens, the weight was constant until exposure temperature 150°C. However, when the temperature exceeded 150°C, the weight started to decreased

drastically. Finally, the ratios of decrease in the specimen with R200, 150HRBQTN and R806 were 80%, 55% and 60%. This result meant that the resin was vaporized by high temperature.

Figure 6 Relationship between the ratio of weight change and each exposure temperature in each specimen

Investigation of Change of Bending Strength

Change of bending strength in each exposure temperature for the exposure time 500h and 1000h was investigated. Figure 7 (a), (b) and (c) show the relationship between bending strength and exposure temperature in each specimen. Bending strength of the specimen with R200 was highest of all specimens. On the other hand, these results showed surprising proof. When the change in color and weight in the exposure temperature was investigated, clear change in each specimen was showed. However, bending strength was constant until the exposure temperature 200°C in any specimens. And the drastic decrease of bending strength was seen in the case of 250°C. This result meant that the change in the color and weight did not always cause the decrease of mechanical properties.

Figure 7 Relationship between bending strength and exposure temperature in each specimen

Investigation of Occurrence of Acoustic Emission (AE)

AE under bending test was measured to investigate the degradation behaviour. Relationships between total number of AE occurrence and exposure temperature are shown in Figure 8 (a), (b) and (c). From these results, it was confirmed that a great number of micro-damages occurred as exposure temperature was higher. However, the total number of AE occurrence decreased in the case of 250°C in any specimens. That is to say, the degradation progressed by the exposure of high temperature. Especially, the total number of AE occurrence of the specimen with R200 was most of all specimens.

Figure 8 Relationship between total number of AE occurrence and exposure temperature in each specimen

DISCUSSIONS

Cross-sectional observation and SEM of cured specimen

Picture and schematic drawing of cross-section of degradation area in R200 specimen are shown in Figure 8. This result is that of the specimens with exposure condition of 200°C, 500h as typical degradation behaviour. In the case of exposure temperature 150°C, the degradation area was not seen in any specimens. However, the thickness of each specimen was thin and not smooth in the case of exposure temperature 200°C. Moreover, many fractures such as delamination were observed in the inside and edge of specimen. Especially, the degradation behaviour of the specimen with R200 was most heavy of all specimens. On the other hand, the fracture inside the specimens with R806 was not observed. As this result, it was found that the matrix in composite material should be selected severely in the application of structure.

Figure 9 (a), (b), (c) and (d) show pictures of SEM observation of degradation area in the specimen with R200. In Figure 9-(a), it was observed that glass fiber appeared on the surface and fell out from the surface. Next, the crack propagation was confirmed from the area where glass fiber fell out in Figure 9-(b). Moreover, glass fiber fracture was observed inside the crack as shown in Figure 9-(c). Next, in Figure 9-(d), the

delamination in the interface between fiber and matrix or in the interface inside the fiber bundle from the edge of the specimen was observed.

Figure 8 Cross-sectional observation of degradation area
after 500h, 200°C in R200 specimen

Figure 9-(a)

Figure 9-(b)

Figure 9-(c)

Figure 9-(d)

Figure 9 SEM photograph of degradation area in the specimen with R200

Degradation mechanism

The degradation mechanisms were discussed on the basis of cross-sectional observation and SEM. Figure 10 shows the schematic illustrations of the degradation mechanism of the surface in the specimen. In 1st stage, the surface of the specimen was heated by the high temperature. In 2nd stage, the matrix was evaporated due to long exposure time and the fiber bundle appeared on the surface. In 3rd stage, the fiber fell out of the matrix. And stress concentration was generated at the bottom of the area where fiber fell out due to longer exposure time. Finally, the crack was generated and propagated at the bottom of the area where fiber fell out.

On the other hand, the schematic illustrations of the degradation mechanism of the edge in the specimen are shown in Figure 11. In 1st stage, the edge of the specimen was heated by the high temperature. In 2nd stage, the matrix was evaporated due to long exposure time same as the surface. In 3rd stage, stress concentration was generated in the area in the interface between fiber and matrix or inside fiber bundle. Finally, the delamination was generated and expanded in the area. Moreover, it was considered that the crack generated on the surface and delamination generated in the edge would be combined afterwards.

The degree of the degradation was different by the kind of matrix. Additionally, the speed of degradation on the surface was faster than that on the edge. It is desirable to improve the thermal resistance of the matrix for the increase of the durability on oxidation degradation because the degradation on oxidation was caused by the evaporation of the matrix in present condition. The comparison between the specimen used in practice and the specimen degraded by high temperature is needed to verify the degradation mechanism. In the future, the work will be performed.

Figure 10 degradation mechanism of the surface

Figure 11 degradation mechanism of the edge

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the oxidation degradation of GFRP was investigated by the promoting test. The color of appearance changed from primary color to brown color. Finally, the specimen was carbonized. In the change of weight, the weight decreased as exposure temperature was higher. However, the bending strength was not changed and showed a constant value. This result revealed that the change in the color and weight did not always cause the decrease of mechanical properties.

About degradation mechanism, it was found that the matrix of the specimen was evaporated by the exposure of the high temperature from the cross-sectional observation and SEM. And the crack and delamination in the interface between fiber and matrix or inside fiber bundle was generated and propagated in the surface and the edge of the specimen because of stress concentration.

The degree of the degradation was different by the kind of matrix. And, the speed of degradation on the surface was faster than that on the edge.

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